

THE ONIGIRI MACHINE

DEVELOPMENT OF WEARABLE DEVICE BY KID’S FRIENDLY DESIGN FOR CHILDREN’S SAFETY

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we developed a wearable device for children under 6 years who are growing up so fast physically to face various experiences in the natural or artificial environment but low ability to describe the events by language exactly what they have experienced at any circumstances to share with their parents. This system will be linked with areal network somebody to react real time when a child faces to inexperienced dangerous events. We adapt biological information with heart rates, three axis sensors to catch physical information such as body movements, GPS and camera on the device. The data from the device could be shared to parents or teachers in the kindergarten afterwards or in real time. We focus on designing the device, which has fascinated form giving, ease to wear and symbolic indication of “being protected” by wearing on. In this paper, we focus to the user-oriented design of the device, which create kid’s friendly and useful function.

Keywords: Kids-Friendly Design, Safety, Mesh Network

INTRODUCTION

In increasing crimes or accidents against children, parents need to consider the way to protect their children and predict what are going to happen to them to know their habits of daily behaviors or related people around them. In Japan, to protect the children from the crimes, most of the primary school children attach security alarm buzzer on their school bags. Most of the primary schools hand the buzzer out to the students as like textbooks. But many of

the children do not care about it and no useful function except making unpleasant noises in surround. It means no more security functions with the alarm buzzer but a simple decoration.

In many cities, increasing working mothers’ children are being taken care by nurseries or kindergartens on their working time. They spend less than 3-4 hours with their child before and after working per day. And under 6 year children they are growing up faster physically but sometimes cannot describe their experiences by telling the stories even though those were scary, happy, surprise or sad to their parents. However, the responsibility of children’s security is on their own parents wherever, whenever or whatever. In this system, we construct a system which can help the parent can confirm their children’s behavior or experiences through a small and charm wearable device connected to areal network with local support team. This device can detect heart rates and behavioral movements of children using heart rates detector and three axis accelerometers. It also has a camera which turns on the power only when a child got a big change of heart rates or movements such as falling down or jumping down. And the visual information from the device can be browsed at home on a secured network program.

For example, if parents receive an emergency e-mail from the children’s device through a server in the kindergarten, they can check the situation by reviewing photographs in real-time. If the situation is really an emergency, the parents can call emergency personnel or police station (Fig.1). In another example, normally if the parents notice a scratch on the kindergartner’s skin after he or she returns home, they may not be able to discover the

reason due to the limited communication abilities of the children. By using our system, the parents can investigate the reason for the scratch. To detect potential emergencies, it is important to acquire the children's activity mode, such as walking, running, training, playing outside, playing inside, or eating. For example, during the sport class, if one child stops movement among the group, we can estimate that the child may have a problem then it may be regarded as an emergency.

DEVELOPMENT OF KID'S FRIENDLY DESIGN

It was very important issue that we proposed a very unique approach to this system such as, designing first and put the advanced technology in a box later. The reason why designing first than the technology is, to make children wear the device as their own willing to be fascinating by attractive form giving and ease to wear. We call it, 'Kids Friendly Design'.

For 'Kid's Friendly Design', we should first concern the weight and size of the device, and secondly about how and where to wear on child's body. Concerning preferred graphical design or decoration for children would be the last step.

Weight and size of the device

To fix the size of the device, we surveyed children's body scale based on Research institute of Human Engineering for quality life in Japan. They've reported all the sizes of average body scale of ages from 0 to 12 from Japanese children since 2005 every year. The width of chest size for 3 year old children is 164mm and 5 year is 176mm. Based on the width of chest, the device should not be exceeded 100mm in any direction.

About the weight, we surveyed the toys

which can be attached on child's neck, most of them are between 30 to 50 grams and which can be attached on their waist, are less than 100 grams. And we also surveyed about the weight to mothers in the kindergarten, 75 percent of them answered under 100 grams can be applied to their children. For references, the alarm buzzer has 45-60 grams and mobile phones for children have 130-150 grams.

How and where to wear the device

To attach on an appropriate position on children's body, we should concern that it should not to bother children's active movements and at the same time the camera on the device should be keep well focused even on the movements. Here we show examples of A and B on the figure 2 and 3.

Design development of the wearable device

Necklace Type

Based on example A, we suggested necklace type of ideas and prototypes (Fig.2). We built up the prototypes by 3D Printer (Dimension 3D Printer BST). This necklace type is not able to fix the camera positioning and have a possibility to be fastened on children's neck by accident.

Shoulder Sac Type

Based on example B on the figure 3, we suggested four kinds of ideas and prototypes. This shoulder sac type is more stable to put a camera on the device and have a diversity of positioning the sensors. Those are well attached on the body, so the sensible weight could be lighter than a real device. B-1 could be made with fabrics or soft rubbers. It fits on the body but the

Figure 1. Overview of the system for detecting potential emergencies children may experience at kindergarten

Figure 2. Design approach in various type of design for device

camera position could be lower than other types A.

Child's chest is high as grownups' knee. If the camera placed lower position on the device, we need to do to control the direction of lens. B-3 is updated idea of B-1. A support belt was added on the other side to improve the stability. B-2 has less space attached on the body than B-3. It has three corners on the shape and each corner connected with belts. And B-4 is applied idea of B-2. It has four corners to spread sensible weight better than others. Figure 4 shows the various shape of device design on children around age of 4-5 body scales.

Build-in a prototype

From the shoulder sac types of design, we finally build the sensors based on the idea B-3. The total weight of the sensors which should be built in, would be at least 90 grams, the necklace type was rejected from the candidates, otherwise it will be a big burden on their neck. Among four ideas of shoulder types, it offers relatively high position of camera and merit of ease to wear. In detail, to decide the size of

device, we made updated sketch of B-3 and made a 3D prototype by 3D printer. To put the sensors safe in a box, the layout of positions were tested. On figure 4. Solving the way to fix on the body, small connection parts were created on the corners. We named it 'Omusbi' (=Onigiri) (Fig.4), meaning of 'Rice ball' or 'Connection' in Japanese. 'Rice ball' is traditional in between lunch and supper snack for children and any ages of people in Japan. 'Connection' is also meaningful function with this study to share information not only between children and parents but also with local supports.

The on-off switch on the rear side is in a tiny hole to be securely turned with an originally designed stick to prevent to be adjusted by somebody else.

Experiment at Kindergarten

We built up 12 hand-made devices, and set up over 30 relay sensors to chase the positioning the devices every 10 meter in the kindergarten. For the final

Figure 3. Design candidates based on the concept of 'fit to body'

user test, we collected about 50 children through ethical research pre-survey of the experiment by their parents. The subjects were average ten children in every age.

To observing the behavior of the children with the devices, there were over 5 staffs attended during the test to check both real physical movements and digital data of positions.

Starting website for reviewing the events in the kindergarten by parents.

The reviewing site was open to the subjects at the beginning of the experiment. It shows every move of children in the kindergarten, for example when they move to hall from the classroom, then the device takes a picture. So, there are number of pictures as they moved the places. However, if the device uses in ordinary life, it should be turn on the power of camera when a child got a big change of heart bit or fall down or jump down on the ground.

Discussion

Weight and size of the device

The goal of designing the devices in this paper, less than 100 grams and 100 mm in every direction for

Figure 4. The final prototype, three cornered called 'Onigiri Machine'

children between ages of 2-6 was achieved. The model with three corners concluded as the final design for children in this study. We adapted the sensors, such as heart rates detector, GPS, three axis accelerometers, camera and micro computer in the device and we still have a possibility that it could be lighter if the sensors we adapt will be lighter and smaller. The final prototype has 97 gram with out the belt.

Figure 5. Children from 2 to 5 years wearing the device, doing exercise at kindergarten during the experiment.

Position of wearing the device

To take heart rates, children will attach a set of wireless detectors on their left side of chest directly. Then the device should be positioned on the right side of chest on outside. The 'Omusbi' device has three corners to fix on the chest so, it does not bother to get signals each other. Figure 4 shows how a child wears the device.

Graphical package for Kid's Friendly Design

Graphical package of device will be also very important for children to make them willing to wear the device by themselves. It will be also a symbolic indication of "Under Protected" when they wear the device. With friendly animal graphics or originally created hero characters would be preferred by children.

Mesh-network to notification between the devices

The devices are all connected to communicate as relayed points to deliver the data to the main server. One of the devices has different movement or different direction at lunch time or at a classroom or in the playground, other devices around it, can report the condition and take pictures (Fig.6).

Privacies when reviewing the photographs on the events

Privacy and personal information was very important issue should be concerned before we started the project, so we developed to adjust the photographs automatically when the data stored in the server except emergent situation. And the device will have a microphone to record the sounds around the children, so we also developed to remove the third part of person's voice.

Figure 6. Mesh-network between the devices.

Future Study

This study is linked with local safety network and usability test by children in the primary schools will be continued in the next stage. The design of Omusbi will be upgraded to be lighter and fancy at anytime better sensors are developed. For user friendly design, various types of devices will be offered to parents. They can choose the functions on and off among the sensors to depends on their children's condition. Each of them will have different experiences and different feeling on the events around them. The device will offer scenes of children's daily experiences only when they were stimulated by unexpected events, to the network by pictures when parents access on secure system. And also staffs of kindergarten or nursery can also access when the children got some changes on their conditions.

Acknowledgement

This study is sponsored by SCOPE (Strategic Information and Communications R&D Promotion Program) of Ministry of Internal affairs and Communications in Japan.

References

SeungHee Lee, Jahee Sohn, Atsushi Usami, Masatoshi Hamanaka(2010) Development of Wearable Device by Kid's friendly Design for Kid's Safety, Human Computer Interaction 2010, Brisbane, Australia

SeungHee Lee, Masatoshi Hamanaka, Yoshiki Iwamoto, Dahyun Kim(2010) Heart-rate Response to Simulated Anxious Events- Development of Kid's Friendly wearable device for children's safety-, Design and Emotion Conference 2010, Chicago, USA

Masatoshi Hamanaka, Yuichi Murakami, Atsushi Usami, Yuji Miura, and SeungHee Lee (2010) System for Detecting Kindergartners' Potential Emergency Situations, World Multi-Conference on Systemics, Cybernetics and Informatics 2010(WMSCI2010), July Florida, USA, Vol. I, pp. 296-301.

Farringdon, J., Moore, A.J., Tilbury, N., Church, J., Biemond, P.D. (1999) Wearable Sensor Badge and Sensor Jacket for Context Awareness. ISWC, pp.107.

Kern, N., Shiele B., Junker Holger, Lukowicz P., Troster G. (2003) Wearable sensing to annotate meeting recordings Euro-Par 2006. LNCS, vol.7, No.5, pp. 263-274. Springer, Heidelberg London.

Wiklund M., (1994) Usability in practice: how companies develop user-friendly products. Academic Press Professional, Inc.